

Public Acceptance and Responsible Mining towards Energy Transition

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Abstract

Critical Raw Materials are essential in the modern-day economy, for digitalization, renewable energy technologies, electric vehicles and long-duration energy storage (LDES) so that our society meets the targets of Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) [1].

The European Commission's (EC) Critical Raw Materials Act (CRMA) sets multiple benchmarks for dependency on just a few third countries for many of its strategic/critical raw materials (CRMs). Member States are supported to secure a resilient, sustainable and ethical supply of CRMs for the transition to a net-zero economy.

For example, Europe is almost 100% reliant on imports of Li for the Li-ion batteries that are central to decarbonising the energy and mobility sectors. A small fraction of European needs can be covered from recycling of End-of-Life (EoL) car batteries, but primary supply still must cover more than 90% of the Li demand. On the other hand, Europe hosts 27 Li hard-rock (pegmatite & Rare-Metal Granite) deposits, representing vast lithium resources (8.8–21.7 Mt Li₂O) [2,3].

Furthermore, the European Commission identified vanadium (V) as a CRM for strategic technologies and sectors in 2017. Europe has a multitude of unexploited, low-grade V-bearing titanomagnetite deposits in Finland, Sweden, Greenland, Norway, Poland, and Ukraine. Most of these deposits have a complex "spiderweb-like" mineral assemblage and without the use of selective blasting and fragmentation, as well as pre-concentration technologies to separate the Ti-rich ilmenite from the V-bearing magnetite, are not economically viable. As a result, despite the potential

recovery of V from steel slag, the targets of the CRMA for more than 10% domestic extraction of V and Ti cannot be met.

It is evident that the goals of the Paris Climate Agreement (PCA) to reduce carbon without more mining and the use of critical minerals cannot be met. However, the European potential to explore and mine its resources and produce strategic and critical elements remains largely untouched, partly due to a reluctant attitude towards mining in several European countries. This attitude is also supported by the fact that some multinational companies involved in mining of CRMs also mine fossil fuels such as coal. On the other hand, it has to be underlined that the leading European companies follow in most cases the principles of responsible exploration, mining, smelting and recycling.

Another aspect that needs to be highlighted is related to the long processes required for obtaining exploration permits. It is known that in most European countries the average lead time from discovery of mineral resources to production often exceeds 15 years.

The major barrier to overcome this negative attitude to exploration and mining is the industry's association with accidents and ecological damage, mainly due to tailings dam failure, mine collapse and CO₂ emissions. More recently, there are accusations that in Indonesia, the country with the largest nickel reserves in which nickel production has nearly tripled since 2020, protected forests in the Sulawesi region are damaged and the livelihoods of the indigenous Bajau people are endangered. Furthermore, other accusations are made in western Australia that during the mining of iron ores part of the ancient Juukan Gorge caves in aboriginal sites was damaged.

Thus, even though many stakeholders agree on the need for more mining of critical / strategic resources, several people are not happy with an operating mine in their backyard.

The social license to operate (SLO) / public acceptance (PA) is an informal social contract first developed in the 1990s to improve the relations between the mining industry and the society. A successful social contract is a prerequisite for the implementation of an exploration / mining project. Most of the disputes among companies and various stakeholders occur as a result of conflicting land uses or due to an advanced risk for affecting the environment, the communities and the ecosystems in the area of concern. Furthermore, estimates indicate that around 50% of critical material resources are located near indigenous people's land [4,5]

The success of an SLO / PA depends on the degree in which the gap among the views of the mining companies and various stakeholders, including the general public, is bridged. The last years, mining companies have taken initiatives to improve their performance and image and to promote stakeholder engagement and company–community relationships. However, a crucial aspect is that the mining industry needs to admit its past faults and increase transparency. So far, more often the

positive economic impacts associated with mining of CRMs, including more jobs and better economic prospects, are highlighted by the industry, but this approach may not be sufficient to reverse the negative attitude [6].

Other important aspects towards SLO / PA include the use of new low-impact mineral exploration and mining technologies, involving also artificial intelligence (AI), that address health, safety and environmental issues and have competitive advantages over the traditional ones. These technologies may involve among others closed circuit drilling, deep-penetrating electro-magnetic survey, muography and the use of drones [7].

It is strongly believed that the PA will be improved if responsible and reliable mining principles are planned so that (i) environmental impacts, associated with many dams hosting beneficiation tailings in several countries are minimized, (ii) risks associated with loss of biodiversity are reduced, (iii) water management in the broader mining industry is optimized and (iv) a breakthrough technological innovation is promoted/generated in all related aspects involving exploration, mining, beneficiation, metallurgy and waste valorization.

This proposed approach is in line with the United Nations Economic Commission for Europe (UNECE) Framework for CRMs that involves among others the establishment of a comprehensive Socio-Environmental-Economic Contract to Operate, integrating impacts on societies and communities, the need for a just transition, climate change mitigation and adaptation, and environmental stewardship [8].

The present paper attempts to highlight all important factors and actions that need to be taken in order to update regulations and standards and apply good practices for responsible mining, in order to meet the goals of the PCA and improve the relations and the trust between the mining industry, the society and all involved stakeholders.

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